

1 Supplemental Materials

2

3

Global cold-chain related SARS-CoV-2 transmission

4

5 Dalang Yu^{1,8,†}, Junwei Zhu^{2,†}, Jianing Yang^{1,8,†}, Yi-Hsuan Pan^{3,†}, Hailong Mu¹,
6 Ruifang Cao¹, Bixia Tang², Guangya Duan^{2,8}, Zi-Qian Hao^{1,8}, Long Dai^{1,7}, Guo-Ping
7 Zhao^{1,5,6}, Ya-Ping Zhang⁴, Wenming Zhao^{2,8,*}, Guoqing Zhang^{1,8,*}, Haipeng Li^{1,8,*}

8

9 ¹National Genomics Data Center, Bio-Med Big Data Center, CAS Key Laboratory of
10 Computational Biology, Shanghai Institute of Nutrition and Health, Chinese
11 Academy of Sciences, Shanghai 200031, China.

12 ²National Genomics Data Center, Beijing Institute of Genomics (China National
13 Center for Bioinformatics), Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100101,
14 China.

15 ³Key Laboratory of Brain Functional Genomics of Ministry of Education, School of
16 Life Science, East China Normal University, Shanghai 200062, China.

17 ⁴Kunming Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Kunming 650227,
18 China.

19 ⁵Key Laboratory of Synthetic Biology, CAS Center for Excellence in Molecular Plant
20 Sciences, Institute of Plant Physiology and Ecology, Chinese Academy of
21 Sciences, Shanghai 200032, China.

22 ⁶School of Life and Health Sciences, Hangzhou Institute for Advanced Study,
23 University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Hangzhou, China.

24 ⁷Shanghai Shenyong Biotechnology Co. LTD, Shanghai 201315, China.

25 ⁸University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing
26 100101, China.

27 [†]Joint Authors.

28 * To whom correspondence should be addressed. Email: lihaipeng@picb.ac.cn;
29 gqzhang@picb.ac.cn; zhaowm@big.ac.cn.

30

31

32 **Supplemental news 1 - News resources for outbreaks**

33 Dalian outbreak

34 Posted date: July 30, 2020

35 Link (in Chinese):

36 <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1673644074775655832&wfr=spider&for=pc>

37

38 **Supplemental news 2 - News resources for outbreaks**

39 The confirmed case in Shenyang

40 Posted date: May 16, 2021

41 Link (in Chinese):

42 <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1699875627551244425&wfr=spider&for=pc>

43

44 Two more confirmed cases in An' hui

45 Posted date: May 16, 2021

46 Link (in Chinese):

47 <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1699919048786611091&wfr=spider&for=pc>

48

49 **Supplemental news 3 - News resources for outbreaks**

50 Covid 19 Coronavirus: Finance Now and Americold cool store at centre of outbreak

51 By: Elizabeth Binning, Chief of staff, NZ Herald

52 Posted date: August 12, 2020

53 Link (in English):

54 <https://www.nzherald.co.nz/nz/covid-19-coronavirus-finance-now-and-americaold-cool-store-at-centre-of-outbreak/XKXFJOPMT3ZW7FJW4BAUX5SUPU/>

55

57 Coronavirus: First outbreak in New Zealand after 102 days sees Auckland put into lockdown

58 By: Greg Heffer

59 Posted date: August 12, 2020

60 Link (in English):

61 <https://news.sky.com/story/coronavirus-breaks-out-again-in-new-zealand-after-102-days-1204701>

62 [1](#)

63

64 **Supplemental Movie**

65 The supplemental movie (in half a minute) shows how to use the CGB to visualize the tree of 783

66 strains non-mutated between January 2019 and May 2021 (Figure 4B).

67

68 **Supplemental Excel file 1**

69 The list of 362 mutation-dormant variants.

70

71 **Supplemental Excel file 2**

72 The list of non-mutated strains shown in Figures 3, 4, and 5.

73

74

75

76 **Figure S1. Case study of the Auckland outbreak.**

77 The samples were filtered by New Zealand first and then only samples before Sep 30,
 78 2020 were kept. The CGB phylogenetic analysis revealed that the highlighted
 79 Auckland clade (CGB55430.55433) has no epidemiological connection with other
 80 New Zealand strains because of its deep split lineage. The subpanel shows enlarged
 81 view of strains found in the Auckland outbreak together with their closely related
 82 sibling lineages found in other countries.

83

84

85

86 **Figure S2. The geographic distribution of the strains that have the same state as**
 87 **the root (*i.e.*, the reference genome sequence NC_045512) ¹.**

88 (A) Presented as absolute counts.

89 (B) Presented as relative frequencies.

90

91

92 **Figure S3. Local putative cold-chain related outbreaks.** The inferred ancestral
 93 strains have the same state as the root (*i.e.*, the reference genome sequence
 94 NC_045512)¹.

95 (A) A case of spillover event from cold-chain in the United Kingdom
 96 (CGB9057.9058).

97 (B) A case of spillover event from cold-chain in the USA (CGB4735.4736).

98

99

100 **Figure S4. The geographic distribution of a D614G mutation-dormant variant.**

101 (A) Presented as absolute counts.

102 (B) Presented as relative frequencies.

103

104

105

106 **Figure S5. Local putative cold-chain related outbreaks.** The inferred ancestral
 107 strains have the same state as a D614G mutation-dormant variant (CGB35.120).

108 (A) A case for spillover event from cold-chain in the India (CGB34228.34229).

109 (B) A case for spillover event from cold-chain in the United Kingdom

110 (CGB21112.21124).

111

112

113

114 **Figure S6. A schematic diagram to show the effect of mis-submitted collection**
 115 **date on identification of mutation-dormant variant.**

116 (A) A case of mis-identified mutation-dormant variant due to mis-submitted collection
 117 date earlier than the true collection date. The upper panel shows the true condition
 118 with the correct collection date, marked by an arrow head. The middle panel
 119 shows that the collection date of the strain (marked by an arrow head) is
 120 mis-submitted. The mis-submitted collection date results in a mis-identified long
 121 non-mutated path (marked in red color). The lower panel shows that the
 122 mis-identified long non-mutated path is removed when the strain with
 123 mis-submitted collection date is removed. Each notch of the branches represents a
 124 mutation.

125 (B) A case of mis-identified mutation-dormant variant due to mis-submitted collection
 126 date later than the true collection date.

127

128

129

130
 131
 132
 133
 134
 135
 136

Figure S7. A schematic diagram to show how the test is performed for the clade A. Each notch of the branches represents a mutation. The node with black circled “A” represents the clade to be tested.

137 Table S1. Evolutionary rate of SARS-CoV-2.

138

Region	Length (sites)	Evolutionary rate (per site per year)
Genome-wide	29,701	9.69×10^{-4}
ORF1a	13,218	5.60×10^{-4}
ORF1b	8,088	3.58×10^{-4}
S	3,822	2.13×10^{-3}
ORF3a	828	3.10×10^{-4}
E	228	1.62×10^{-5}
M	669	4.80×10^{-4}
ORF6	186	9.01×10^{-5}
ORF7a	366	4.56×10^{-3}
ORF7b	132	4.22×10^{-3}
ORF8	366	4.52×10^{-3}
N	1,260	2.78×10^{-3}
ORF10	117	9.69×10^{-4}
noncoding	441	6.07×10^{-3}

139

140

141

Table S2. Mutation-dormant variants in the Delta Variant of Concern (VOC).

Index	CGB ID	Total length (days)	Num. of identical strains	Date of start	Date of end	Characteristic mutations	Other mutations [†]
1	CGB531065.591827	160	34	2021/3/5	2021/8/12	G21987A	Mut Set 01,02
2	CGB591827.645203	158	98	2021/3/8	2021/8/13	G21987A, C21846T	Mut Set 01,02
3	CGB736525.830096	144	55	2021/3/21	2021/8/12	A29700G, T14014G, C6040T, C7926T	Mut Set 01,02
4	CGB744625.824957	144	474	2021/3/30	2021/8/21	G21987A, C21846T, A25003G, C6408T	Mut Set 01,02
5	CGB736525.839242	141	283	2021/3/24	2021/8/12	A29700G, T14014G, C6040T, C7926T, G21987A	Mut Set 01,02
6	CGB843452.957320	134	126	2021/3/30	2021/8/11	G21987A, G26107C, A27507C, C21897T	Mut Set 01,02
7	CGB692105.692163	134	4,582	2021/4/9	2021/8/21	G21987A, C21846T, C7851T	Mut Set 01,02
8	CGB692105.758869	132	3,984	2021/4/12	2021/8/22	G21987A, C21846T, C7851T, T17040C	Mut Set 01,02
9	CGB759162.841282	131	89	2021/4/10	2021/8/19	G21987A, C27527T, G1048T, C27526T, C4455T	Mut Set 01,02
10	CGB763421.763514	130	929	2021/4/14	2021/8/22	G21987A, G2336A, G17331T	Mut Set 01,02
11	CGB685958.801178	118	577	2021/4/15	2021/8/11	G21987A, G24928T, C29253T	Mut Set 01,02
12	CGB801082.864797	116	779	2021/4/23	2021/8/17	G21987A, C21846T, C7851T, T17040C, T4237C	Mut Set 01,02
13	CGB844959.875198	115	112	2021/4/25	2021/8/18	G21987A, C21846T, C7851T, G22051C	Mut Set 01,02
14	CGB580144.642966	112	263	2021/4/1	2021/7/22	C9891T, C5184T, T11418C, C11514T, C22227T, C13019T, A5584G, G21987A, C22792T	Mut Set 01
15	CGB885562.885688	109	239	2021/5/4	2021/8/21	G21987A, G27566T, C27629A, G12718T, G11365T, G2944A, T15882G	Mut Set 01,02

[†]Mut Set 01 includes 23 mutations: C3037T, A23403G, C14408T, C241T, T22917G, G28881T, T27638C, C23604G, C27752T, C22995A, A28461G, T26767C, G29742T, C25469T, G24410A, C21618G, G29402T, C16466T, G15451A, G210T, GATTTC28248-, AGTTCA22029-, and A28271-.

Mut Set 02 includes 11 mutations: G28916T, C27874T, C7124T, G4181T, G9053T, C8986T, C10029T, C19220T, A11332G, A11201G, and C640.

Reference

- 1 Wu, F. *et al.* A new coronavirus associated with human respiratory disease in China. *Nature* **579**, 265-269 (2020).